

Measurements of azimuthal anisotropy via two-particle
correlations in $p+p$ and $p+Au$ collisions at
 $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV with PHENIX at RHIC

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Abstract

A relativistic heavy ion collider such as the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) is a unique tool to provide high-energy ion beams to create new deconfined states of quarks and gluons. Quark–gluon plasma (QGP) is one of the states predicted by lattice quantum chromodynamics (QCD) to exist at extremely high temperature and pressure. QGP behaves like an ideal fluid with low viscosity and the distribution of the final-stage particles provides an initial state as well as bulk properties of QGP.

As one of the experimental probes to hint at the initial condition of QGP, azimuthal anisotropy, which is calculated by using two-particle correlations, has been proposed and is well established with the Fourier expansion coefficient, v_n . Some order of nonzero v_n is considered to be one of the most critical pieces of evidence of QGP creation because the angular anisotropy originates from the initial geometry eccentricity of QGP. As a consequence of heavy ion collision, a rugby-ball-shape QGP is formed in the overlapping region of two colliding nuclei. The rugby-ball shape is detected as the second order of the Fourier cosine coefficient v_2 , and thus it is called “elliptic flow” because it can be used to describe the proportion of the particle distribution discharged on the basis of the reaction plane of second order. Meanwhile, small systems such as $p+p$ or $p+\text{Au}$ collisions have been regarded as a nonflow background measurement of QGP because the collision systems are believed to be too small to create QGP. However, recent analyses of small system data

show a significant value of v_2 that cannot be explained purely by the backgrounds at high-multiplicity events. The CMS experiment reported the first measurement of the relation between multiplicity and the near-side long-range ridge structure at the smallest size of the collision system, $p+p$, as an indication of v_2 , which is expected from the QGP origin. However, the ATLAS experiment reported that its observed v_2 did not show multiplicity dependence originating from the initial geometry of the QGP, although it did show the ridge of $p+p$ and $p + \text{Pb}$ in high-multiplicity events. This discrepancy has not been resolved yet and remains as an open question.

The PHENIX experiment also measured v_2 in small systems— $^3\text{He}+\text{Au}$, $d+\text{Au}$, and $p+\text{Au}$ —at mid-rapidity in high-multiplicity events using the event-plane method. The PHENIX-measured v_2 in the small systems show that the size of v_2 cannot be explained by the background as in other experimental results. However, the multiplicity and/or p_T dependencies do not necessarily behave systematically as expected from the QGP origin. Therefore, v_2 measured in small systems appears to be dominated by the nonflow effect. In general, the nonflow effect is suppressed by $1/\sqrt{N}$, where N is the number of particles. Because the multiplicity of small systems is significantly smaller than that in heavy ion collisions, the nonflow effect is expected to be dominating in small systems. Therefore, nonflow effects need to be more carefully evaluated in small systems than in large systems owing to their large contribution to observed v_2 .

In this thesis, the v_2 values are measured in $p+\text{Au}$ and $p+p$ at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV

with various $\Delta\eta$ ranges to establish the nonflow effect. $\Delta\eta$ is the opening rapidity angle between two particles emitted from a given collision. The v_2 values are analyzed by using the two-particle correlation method, and the results show that v_2 has a strong dependence on $\Delta\eta$ in small systems, most likely because of different nonflow contributions depending on $\Delta\eta$. As a result, the different v_2 values obtained at a given rapidity range depend on $\Delta\eta$. Because only one flow value at a rapidity range is possible, the difference in the v_2 values indicates that the size of the nonflow effect is different for different $\Delta\eta$ values. Moreover, the reference fit method is applied to the measured flow interpretations to enable a more sophisticated interpretation for small systems. The reference fit method subtracts the low-multiplicity correlations from the high-multiplicity correlations to identify the difference between those two correlation functions.

In summary, the resulting v_2 values show strong $\Delta\eta$ dependence. This is an indication of the large fraction of nonflow effects in v_2 for $p+\text{Au}$. The newly proposed nonflow subtraction method in this thesis and the reference fit method largely removes the nonflow effect compared to the template fit method, but it cannot yet remove the nonflow effect completely. However, most of the subtracted v_2 obtained with the reference fit method shows strong centrality dependence. Therefore, the extracted v_2 values using the reference fit method are less biased than those obtained in the previous ATLAS analysis. Our study of the v_2 values can help to understand QGP in small systems.

1 Introduction

I Quantum Chromodynamics and Quark–Gluon Plasma

One of the main topics in nuclear physics is the search for the properties of the early stage of the Universe. High-energy heavy ion colliders such as the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) and the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) are ideal testing grounds to study the initial state of the Universe because heavy ion colliders provide high temperature and pressure similar to the conditions after a few nanoseconds since the Universe's birth.

At the very beginning of the Big Bang, both temperature and pressure were extremely high. After the Big Bang, reheating started until the Universe reached a temperature high enough to generate free, unbound elementary particles. This deconfined condition, known as the quark–gluon plasma (QGP) [1], is believed to be the state of the initial phase of the Universe. As time progresses, the Universe expands as a result of the Big Bang; therefore, the temperature and the pressure gradually dropped to the present conditions (2.73 K, measured by the microwave background) [2]. Therefore, the quarks and the gluons, which are the fundamental particles, lost their kinetic energy and started to bind to each other and make composite particles such as protons and neutrons [3].

Quarks have six flavors—up (*u*), down (*d*), charm (*c*), strange (*s*), top (*t*), and bottom (*b*)—and three color charges; red (*r*), green (*g*), and blue (*b*). These quarks

cannot be observed alone experimentally because they always make compound particles, which are called hadrons, that satisfy color charge summation to be white (neutral or colorless) [1, 4].

The hadrons are categorized into two family groups in accordance to how they satisfy the colorless condition. The wave function of the first case, which is made of three quarks, is described as

$$\psi^{qqq} = (rgb - rbg + gbr - grb + brg - bgr)/\sqrt{6}, \quad (1)$$

where $r(g,b)$ is red(green, blue) charges. This wave function allows an antisymmetry state as well. The antistates of Eq. (1) are given by

$$\psi^{\bar{q}\bar{q}\bar{q}} = (\bar{r}\bar{g}\bar{b} - \bar{r}\bar{b}\bar{g} + \bar{g}\bar{b}\bar{r} - \bar{g}\bar{r}\bar{b} + \bar{b}\bar{r}\bar{g} - \bar{b}\bar{g}\bar{r})/\sqrt{6}, \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{r} (\bar{g}, \bar{b})$ is antistate of $r(g, b)$. The hadron that allows the antistate to also be white is a baryon.

Another kind of hadron, composed of one quark and one antiquark, is described as

$$\psi^{q\bar{q}} = (r\bar{r} + g\bar{g} + b\bar{b})/\sqrt{3}. \quad (3)$$

This wave function, in contrast to that of the baryon, does not allow an antisymmetry wave function to be colorless. The hadron family that satisfies this condition is called the meson [5].

Quantum chromodynamics (QCD) is a gauge theory that explains the strong interactions between gluons and quarks. The strong force is mediated by the glu-

ons, which not only carry the color charges but also interact with themselves. The self-interacting feature of the force carrier of QCD is different from that of quantum electrodynamics (QED), which explains the interactions between charges and photons [6].

The electric charge in a dielectric substance creates pairs of particles oppositely charged to the source charge. The interactions within these dipoles that surround this source give a blocking effect on the size of the source charge. As a result, the effective value of the source charge measured at a long distance seems to be smaller than the real value. This blocking impact, called the “screening” effect, is observed in QED.

However, because the gluons self-interact with themselves, the polarization of QCD can have two models. A quark can create pairs of particles that have opposite color charges to the source. At the same time, a quark can also produce particles that have different colors while maintaining the whiteness of the total sum of the color charges. Figure 1 explains that the gluons are actually “antiscreened” so that the size of the color charges are larger at a farther distance than the original size of the source. The QCD antiscreening effect means that the intensity of the strong interaction decreases as momentum transfer increases and finally disappears asymptotically. This asymptotically diminished intensity is the “asymptotic freedom,” which is one of the critical features of QCD. Therefore, we can reach a QGP by using relativistic heavy ion collisions as large momentum exchanging circumstance [3, 7].

Figure 1. Cartoon showing the antiscreening effect of the quark. $r(g, b)$ are the color charges, and $\bar{r}(\bar{g}$ and $\bar{b})$ are their antistatuses.

Figure 2 shows the measurement summary of the running coupling constant α_s as a function of the momentum transfer factor, Q [8]. Generally, the perturbatively calculated cross section of QCD is described by a power series

$$d\sigma_{\text{QCD}} = \sum_{n=n_0}^{\infty} \alpha_s^n A_n, \quad (4)$$

where A_n is the coefficient determined by the Feynman rules, α_s is the coupling constant defined as $g_s^2/4\pi$, and g_s is the effective size of the color charge. When Q is large enough ($Q^2 \gg 100 \text{ GeV}^2$), α_s as a function of momentum transfer Q is

$$\alpha_s(Q^2) \cong \frac{1}{\beta_0 \ln(Q^2/\Lambda_{\text{QCD}}^2)}, \quad (5)$$

where Λ_{QCD} is the QCD scale and β_0 is $(33 - 2n_f)/6\pi$, with n_f determined by the flavors of a quark. The QCD scale is determined by the coupling constants obtained

experimentally. One of the latest measurements gives $\Lambda_{\text{QCD}} = 213.9 \text{ MeV}$ when $\alpha_s = 0.1189 \pm 0.0010$. As Q increases, the intensity of the strong interactions is eliminated, so the coupling constant α_s decreases and QCD can be described perturbatively. However, in the small- Q region, because the coupling constant becomes dominant, a nonperturbative interpretation is needed [7].

Figure 2. Summary of the running coupling constant α_s as a function of momentum transfer Q [8].

Although there is no analytic evidence, isolated quarks are never found. However,

there is a calculation for the potential energy between a quark and antiquark pair in the (2+1) flavor lattice QCD. Lattice QCD is a gauge field theory that is the space–time transfer into the grid structure. Unlike other quantum field theories, lattice field theory does not distinguish time and space and expresses the continuous system as a grid structure. The potential energy $V(R)$ at a finite temperature T (when T is larger than the critical temperature, T_c) is

$$V(R) = V_0 - \frac{\alpha_s}{R} + \sigma_0 R, \quad (6)$$

where V_0 , α_s , and σ_0 are independent free parameters. The potential energy increases linearly until R reaches some critical point. Energetically, beyond the critical point, generation of the quark and antiquark pair is more favored.

This qualitative understanding describes the interactions between the heavy quarks particularly well. The connection between the quark and the antiquark can be thought of as two quarks connected by one string. When the combined $q\bar{q}$ pair is forced to separate, the potential between those two particles will increase. At the certain distance, splitting of the $q\bar{q}$ pair is preferable and new pairs are created with other $q\bar{q}$ pairs. In other words, the strong force increases with the distance between the two quarks, thus eliminating the possibility of measuring isolated quarks. Therefore, the $q\bar{q}$ pair linear potential energy always gives measured hadrons in a color charge “color-singlet” state. This is so-called “(color) confinement” and it is another feature of QCD [1].

II Signature of the QGP Formations

It is crucial that the coupling constant (α_s) of QCD is reduced under high-momentum-exchanging conditions. This property implies that, in very high energy collisions, in which an enormous amount of momentum is transferred, the quarks within the hadrons are asymptotically free and independent of each other because the coupling constant becomes smaller. This small coupling constant enables the color charge interaction to be perturbatively calculated over a short distance (large momentum transfer), so the prediction of QCD is thought to be particularly accurate under conditions of high momentum transfer.

Therefore, if the temperature is high enough, the thermal-kinetic energy breaks out the hadron and creates the QGP. This phase transition is expected as a product of asymptotic freedom of perturbative QCD (pQCD) and considered to become a state of matter in a few seconds after the Big Bang. Moreover, at a collision energy that exceeds the critical temperature (T_c), the probability of producing more massive quarks is increased, so it is not limited to the generation of lower mass quarks [3].

Figure 3 shows the energy density of QCD matter with 2, 3, and 2+1 flavors of quarks calculated by lattice QCD [9]. The differential value of ϵ/T^4 as a function of temperature T changes dramatically at the critical temperature T_c . This implies that a phase transition occurs at T_c , from the hadronic system to the QGP.

One key observation made by the Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment (PHENIX) is that heavy ion collisions can create an almost ideal fluid

Figure 3. Calculation of the energy density ϵ , which is normalized by T^4 , where T is the temperature of the system [9].

with very low viscosity. In the following section, the signature of QGP formation is described in detail [10].

II.A Collectivity and flow

Multiplicity and centrality

In heavy ion collisions, the initial collision geometry plays an important role in understanding the relationship between the generated QGP and the measured collective response of the particles. Figure 4 shows a schematic diagram of the two heavy ions colliding with each other [9]. The impact parameter b is defined as the distance between the centers of the two nuclei and can describe the overlapping region of the collision. Inelastic scattering occurs when the impact parameter is smaller than the sum of the two nuclei radii. If b is close to 0, almost all the nucleons in the smaller

nucleus will participate in the collision, and this is called a central collision. In contrast, if a limited number of particles join the collision, this is called a peripheral collision. Particles located in the overlapping region and involved in the collision are called “participants,” while the others are called “spectators.” Figure 5 shows a schematic view of collision of two heavy ions as seen from the beam axis. From left to right, the collision “centrality” moves from “central” to “peripheral.” Here “centrality” refers to the overlapping area of the two-particle collision as seen from the beam view.

Figure 4. Simplified cartoon before (left) and after (right) the nuclear collision [11].

Figure 5. Schematic view of the two heavy ion collisions from the beam viewpoint.

Because the intermediate range of the strong force is short, only the participants

interact with each other. Therefore, the size of the generated QGP will heavily depend on the impact parameter. This limited range of the strong force means that the final-stage measurable particle multiplicity is highest in the most central collisions, because that is when the nucleons are most likely to interact with each other. Therefore, the charged particle multiplicity is defined as the “centrality,” which is the experimentally determined factor of the impact parameter [11]. Figure 6 shows the result of calculations performed using A Multi-Phase Transport (AMPT) model for the relation between impact parameter and multiplicity [12]. The particle multiplicity is strongly related to the impact parameter, which controls the size of the generated hot and dense matter.

Figure 6. Relation between impact parameter and multiplicity calculated by AMPT.

Azimuthal anisotropy

The measurement of the particle azimuthal anisotropy distribution is a powerful tool for proving QGP generation given the initial geometry of the collision. Figure 7 describes the case in which two nuclei collide with a finite impact parameter. The red and yellow almond shape between the two blue remainders is the generated hot and dense matter. The XY plane is the “reaction plane,” which is defined by the impact parameter vector and the beam axis, Z . The overlapping region in the beam direction (Z axis) has an elliptical shape. If this created substance is the QGP, then the density inside is uniform. The minor axis of the QGP shape is expected to exhibit a larger initial pressure gradient compared to that of major axis because of the uniform density inside. Consequently, the final-stage particles that the route angle has a larger transverse component to the Y axis will have the higher momentum. In other words, if this generated QGP reaches thermal stability while conserving the initial geometry information, one could get this information from the measured azimuthal anisotropy at the final stage. Because the QGP behaves like almost ideal fluid with low viscosity, the particle anisotropy has a “flow,” which is the factor describing how the energy, momentum, and number of particles vary with direction. In particular, “elliptic flow” refers to the flow that is not uniform along the beam axis.

The Fourier expansion of the n_{th} order of the cosine modulation coefficient is well established for explaining the azimuthal distribution of the particles to the n_{th}

Figure 7. Cartoon describing heavy ion collision. The grid shows the reaction plane. The almond shape denotes the participants and the blue shapes are the remainders.

order of the reaction plane, Ψ_R . The relationship between the Fourier expansion and the azimuthal particle distribution can be shown as

$$E \frac{d^3 N}{dp^3} = \frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{d^3 N}{dp_T dy} \left(1 + 2 \sum_n v_n(p_T) \cos[n(\phi - \Psi_R)] \right), \quad (7)$$

where p_T is the transverse momentum, N is the number of the particles, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle of the measured particle. The coefficients of the each n_{th} order of cosine modulations, “ v_n ,” are the intensity of the initial geometry fluctuations. The first order of the cosine coefficient is the directed flow component, which indicates the deconfinement transition in QCD, the second order of the cosine coefficient is the elliptical shape component of the initial geometry fluctuations, and the third order of the cosine coefficient is the triangular shape component of the initial geometry fluctuations.

The azimuthal particle pair distribution in one event, $dN_{\text{pair}}/d\phi$, is shown as

$$\frac{dN_{\text{pair}}}{d\phi} \propto 1 + 2 \sum_{n=1} v_n \cos(n[\phi - \Psi_n]), \quad (8)$$

where Ψ_n is the n_{th} order of the “event plane.” From the relation in Eq. (8), the event plane is the angular direction in which the most significant numbers of particles at the final stage are emitted. Unlike the reaction plane which is defined at theoretical circumstance, the event plane is determined at the experimental situation. The “elliptic flow,” which explains the almond shape of the generated QGP, is the second harmonic cosine coefficient, which is v_2 . Because “elliptic flow” is considered as a propagation of the initial shape component of the QGP to the final stage, the measured v_2 is a powerful piece of evidence for the QGP creation.

Heavy ion collisions

In heavy ion systems such as Au + Au collisions, the measured v_2 values exhibit a strong centrality dependence. Figure 8 shows the result of v_2 measured in Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV [13]. The v_2 measured by using two particles with an opening rapidity angle ($\Delta\eta$) >2 gives the largest v_2 at mid-centrality, because the generated QGP’s shape has the smallest value of the ratio between minor axis and major axis at mid-centrality. Therefore, the elliptic shape component, v_2 , shows the largest value at mid-centrality. However, v_2 measured without any $\Delta\eta$ condition exhibits similar behavior up to mid-centrality and exhibits stable values and suddenly increases at the most peripheral collisions. The discrepancy between the v_2

measured with large $\Delta\eta$ and that without $\Delta\eta$ is a clear indication of the near-side jet effect in heavy ion collisions, and it is dominant in peripheral events. The peripheral events in Au + Au collisions can be assumed as small systems from the multiplicity aspect. Therefore, the near-side jet effect, which is one of the candidates for the nonflow effect, which is measured as anisotropy of particle correlations but does not originate from the QGP flow, would be dominant in low-multiplicity events such as in small systems.

Figure 8. Charged hadron v_2 in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV as a function of centrality, showing the rapidity gap dependence between two particles [13].

II.B Small-system measurement

As introduced in Section II.A, elliptic flow is one of the most persuasive data for QGP creation in heavy ion collisions. Many studies show evidence of QGPs being

generated in large collision systems such as Cu + Au and Au + Au from RHIC experiments [14, 15] and Pb + Pb from LHC experiments [16, 17]. However, small systems such as $p+p$, $p+Au$ or $d+Au$ were thought to be too small to produce QGP, especially because the size of the proton is too small to provide an overlapping region in a collision event.

However, the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) revealed a near-side ($\Delta\phi \sim 0$), long-range (wide $\Delta\eta$) “ridge” structure, especially for high-multiplicity events in $p+p$ collisions [18]. The ridge, c_2 , is the nonzero coefficient of the $\cos(2\Delta\phi)$ modulations in the two-dimensional, two-particle correlations as a function of $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\eta$, which are the angular difference between the measured particle and the trigger particle, which has the largest p_T in one event. The relation between ridge and v_2 is evaluated at Section III.A.

Figure 9 shows the two-particle correlations measured at $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 7$ TeV by the CMS experiments [18]. The correlation functions for the high-multiplicity events show a clear near-side ridge structure over an extended range of $\Delta\eta$. The peak located at the origin, $(\Delta\phi, \Delta\eta) \sim (0, 0)$, is the (trigger) near-side jet. Because the near-side jet can provide a nonzero coefficient of $\cos(2\Delta\phi)$ modulations, the wide range of $\Delta\eta$ is the essential feature of the ridge structure. The away-side jet, which is located at $(\Delta\phi, \Delta\eta) \sim (0, \pi)$ is smeared over a broad range of rapidity owing to the parton center-of-mass system being shifted to the center of mass of the collision.

Figure 9. 2-D two-particle correlation functions for $p+p$ at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 7$ TeV: (a) $p_T > 0.1$ GeV/ c , (b) $1 < p_T < 3$ GeV/ c , (c) high-multiplicity events with $p_T > 0.1$ GeV/ c , and (d) high-multiplicity events with $1 < p_T < 3$ GeV/ c [18].

Because the near-side jet in the particle-pair distribution is dominant in small systems, both CMS and A Toroidal LHC ApparatuS (ATLAS) experiments use the flow subtraction method on their $p+p$ and $p + \text{Pb}$ analyses [18, 19, 20, 21]. The flow subtraction method is sophisticated rejection of the nonflow contributions from high-multiplicity events. The subtraction method used by the ATLAS experiment is described and compared to the reference fit method, which is designed by PHENIX's Tsukuba group.

The ATLAS experiment also measured the near-side ridge structure. Figure 10 shows one of the ATLAS results for two-particle correlations of a small system with $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 13$ TeV [20]. The vertical axis gives the correlation functions normalized to zero. The left spectrum in Figure 10 is the result of a low-multiplicity (minimum-bias) event, while the right spectrum is the result of a high-multiplicity event. Although the correlation results show an apparent dependence of the multiplicity with similar trends to those of the Au + Au collision v_2 observation, the ATLAS v_2 measurement demonstrated in Figure 11 implies a vanishing multiplicity dependence of v_2 after the nonflow background subtraction.

Figure 10. ATLAS “ridge” measurement of $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 13$ TeV [20].

If the ridge structure in small systems has the QGP as its source, the measured v_2 is expected to have a multiplicity dependence because the gluons mediate only the short-range strong force. Therefore, although a multiplicity-dependent ridge structure is found, the result of the ATLAS experiment may contradict that the

Figure 11. ATLAS v_2 measurement of $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 13$ and 2.78 TeV as a function of transverse momentum and multiplicity [20].

collectivity in a small system is coming from the QGP.

Previous results from PHENIX

PHENIX also has made many small-system v_2 measurements. The results of $p+Au$, $d+Au$, and ^3He+Au 0–5% centrality events for v_2 as a function of p_T have been published and compared to each other [22]. Table 1 lists the data sets collected by PHENIX. The $d+Au$ collision beam energy scan data was taken and published in

Table 1. PHENIX small-system data collections.

Energy (GeV)	$p+p$	$p+Al$	$p+Au$	$d+Au$	${}^3He+Au$
19.6				○	
39				○	
62.4				○	
200	○	○	○	○	○

2017 [23].

However, there is a possible argument about the nonflow effect calculation in small systems. The near-side jet can be one of the nonflow effects. Figure 12 is the result of $d+Au$ beam energy scan data measured v_2 , showing the dependence on centrality. As recalled in the ATLAS case, if the QGP flow dominates the measured collectivity, a strong relationship between v_2 and multiplicity should be found. However, the beam energy scan results in $d+Au$ do not provide a systematic behavior of v_2 as a function of the centrality. Therefore, we can conclude that the measured v_2 consists of not only the QGP flow but also another effect, which is called the nonflow effect. Because the $d+Au$ energy scan results do not quantify the nonflow effect from the measurement, the only possible way to estimate the nonflow is through simulations.

Figure 12. PHENIX v_2 measurement in Run-16 $d+Au$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$, 62.4, 39 GeV, and 19.6 GeV as a function of centrality.

v_2 pseudo-rapidity dependence (η)

At PHENIX, the pseudo-rapidity (rapidity, η) dependence of v_2 of the $d+Au$ beam energy scan data has been measured. Figure 13 shows v_2 as a function of the rapidity measured at 0–5% centrality of $d+Au$ collisions at 39-, 62.4-, and 200-GeV [23]. From left to right, each figure represents the measured v_2 values are calculated from the event-plane method using the three-subsystem. As the collision energy

becomes smaller, the size of the evaluated v_2 for $\eta < 0$ becomes diminished. The hydrodynamic calculation, from the AMPT simulation, well describes the overall trends of the v_2 dependence on η .

Figure 13. v_2 for the high-multiplicity d +Au events at (a) 39 GeV, (b) 62.4 GeV, and (c) 200 GeV [23].

At the measured ridge structure which is defined at the two-particle correlation method, the η differences between the trigger particle and associated particle required $\Delta\eta \geq 2$ for the elimination of the near-side jet effect. The other experiments like CMS [18, 19] and ATLAS [20, 21], measure the two-particle correlation as a function of $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\eta$. Therefore, one can say the $\Delta\eta$ which is determined between the two particles is the critical constraint to identify the long-range ridge, which is the evidence of the QGP.

III PHENIX p +Au analysis

There have been many studies to search for and quantify the features of the QGP. The azimuthal anisotropies give a mathematical interpretation of the QGP initial

condition and its bulk properties.

In heavy ion collisions, measured collectivities are directly related to the QGP and the flow information. Therefore, many people have concluded that a QCD phase transition occurs in relativistic heavy ion collisions and that the generated QGP behaves nearly as a perfect fluid with low viscosity. The lower limit of the phase transition temperature, i.e., critical temperature, can be predicted by using lattice QCD, and experimental results support this theoretical calculation.

However, there remain uncertainties about the “size” of the lower limit of the QGP creation. The CMS experiment revealed an azimuthal anisotropic behavior, called a “ridge,” for $p+p$ collisions, which is the smallest system size, at a collision energy of $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 13$ TeV [18]. However, the v_2 measurement with the jet effect subtraction done for the ATLAS experiments implies a collective behavior of small systems that still has uncertainty with respect to evidence of QGP creation [20]. pQCD (asymptotic freedom) allows a lower limit for the collision energy. The small-system v_2 results from the RHIC experiment can provide meaningful interpretations about the source of the measured v_2 because the range of the collision energy of RHIC is a factor of ~ 1000 smaller than that of the LHC.

However, small-system results from PHENIX give only predictions about the collectivity, which is strongly contaminated from the “nonflow” effect based on the simulations. Therefore, the possibility of a quantitative determination of the flow component in small systems is still under discussion.

The PHENIX collaboration published v_2 and v_3 data from p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV as a function of p_T in the 0–5% centrality region [24]. The measured v_2 in the p +Au data was compared with other small-system results, ^3He +Au and d +Au, at 0–5% centrality. The previous studies show meaningful v_3 differences among several small systems, which indicate that the initial geometry propagates to the measured collectivity. However, there were no discussions about the centrality and pseudo-rapidity dependence of the examined v_2 , even though these can provide strong support for the creation of the QGP.

The published v_2 data for PHENIX small systems are always measured by using the event-plane method, which uses the relative azimuthal particle distributions to the event plane, which is determined by the number of particles of the angular distribution. Therefore, the two-particle correlation method needs a consistency check with the publication results for proof of the method. PHENIX’s previous publication for p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV shows v_2 as a function of p_T in the 0–5% centrality region. Therefore, v_2 as a function of p_T with a centrality dependence shows the result of a consistency check with previous publications.

In this dissertation, we present the azimuthal anisotropies of the charged hadrons of p + p and p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV as a function of rapidities with the centrality dependence using the PHENIX detectors. The measured v_2 can provide a new approach to interpreting the flow component in the quantified v_2 values for small systems.

2 RHIC and PHENIX

I RHIC

RHIC was built at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) as the world’s first heavy ion ($u > 100$) accelerator operated by the United States of America. Currently, it is providing the second highest collision energy in the world. RHIC is composed of two rings: the “blue” ring, where particles circulate clockwise, and the “yellow” ring, where particles circulate anticlockwise. As shown in Figure 14, counter-rotating particle beams are designed to cross each other at six intersections [25]. Experiments using PHENIX are conducted at an interaction located at the 8 o’clock position of RHIC. At RHIC, many types of particles are provided for collision—from $A = 1$ (protons) to $A = 238$ (uranium). RHIC has a circumference of 3833.8 m and consists of 396 dipoles and 492 quadrupole superconducting magnets to guide and focus the heavy ion beams. At a magnetic field of 3.458 T, the beam energy is 100 GeV/nucleon for fully electron stripped gold ions and 250 GeV for (polarized) protons. These magnets are cooled by ~ 4.2 K helium. For increasing collision energy, the magnetic field is increased accordingly, up to 3.5 T, which corresponds to Au + Au collisions of 200 GeV and $p+p$ collisions to 500 GeV. The ion bunches are stored in the rings for 6 to 12 h and collided at six intersections. The beam bunch luminosity L is related to the number of events N , the cross section σ by

$$N = L\sigma. \tag{9}$$

Figure 14. Layout of RHIC at BNL. The PHENIX experiments are located at the eight o'clock position [25].

II PHENIX Overview

PHENIX is one of two currently operating experiments at BNL. Beam and side views of the PHENIX detector systems are depicted in Figure 15. Particles of interest emitted from collisions are measured at four subsystems in PHENIX: the east and west arms and the north and south arms. The PHENIX east and the west arms are independent spectrometers of the central arm, which cover mid-rapidity and measure electrons, photons, and hadrons, as shown in the left panel of Figure 15. The PHENIX north and south arms are the other two spectrometers intended to cover forward and backward rapidity and measure muons. Because the target (a

heavy ion) is projected from the north, and a projectile comes from the south in asymmetric runs, the south arm is referred to as the heavy-ion-going side (or target-going side or Au-going side for the case in which Au is the target) and the north arm is called the projectile-going side (or p -going side for the case in which a proton is the projectile). The north arm is also called the forward-rapidity side while the south arm is called the backward-rapidity side.

Figure 15. Beam (left) and side (right) views of the PHENIX subsystems [26].

II.A PHENIX Magnet System

The PHENIX's magnet system consists of three spectrometer magnets: the central magnet(CM), the north muon magnet, and the south muon magnet. The radial magnetic field is always controlled to provide the “zero field” near the collision vertex.

III Forward and Backward Subsystems

III.A Beam–beam counter

The primary role of the beam–beam counter (BBC) along the vertex positions of the beam axis (z) is to measure the multiplicity at forward and backward rapidities ($3 < |\eta| < 3.9$) to determine event categorization, centrality, as well as the vertex positions of the beam axis (z). In experiments, the multiplicity is used for defining the centrality. The BBC is composed of two independent subsystems: BBCN (BBC north, $3 < \eta < 3.9$) is placed at the north and BBCS (BBC south, $-3.9 < \eta < -3$) is located at the south. Each BBC has 64 Cherenkov radiators, each of which consists of a photomultiplier tube (Hamamatsu R6178) with 3 cm of quartz on top. By taking into consideration that the diameter of the beam pipe is 10 cm, the outer diameter of the BBC is set at 30 cm and the inner diameter at 10 cm. The BBC operates under the circumstance of a very high level of radiation and a high magnetic field, because the BBC is located around the beam pipe near the collision point just behind the PHENIX magnet [26].

III.B FVTX

The Forward silicon Vertex Tracker (FVTX), the tracking system of the innermost side of the forward/backward detectors of PHENIX, provides a wide range of acceptance ($1 < |\eta| < 3$, full azimuthal coverage). The FVTX consists of two separate subsystems, which are positioned in the forward direction (FVTX-N, $1 < \eta < 3$)

Figure 16. Photograph of the BBC (left) and front view schematic of the BBC (right).

and the backward direction ($-3 < \eta < -1$). Each FVTX system has four stations (from 0 to 3) with a total of eight layers (two layers per station) of silicon mini-strip sensors. One layer corresponds to 24 silicon mini-strip sensors, and one silicon sensor is composed of two columns of mini-strips, each of which has a $75\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ pitch in the radial direction and 24 angles in the (ϕ) direction varying from 3.4 mm at the innermost radius to 11.5 mm at the outermost radius [26].

IV Central Arm Detectors

The PHENIX central magnet generates a magnetic field parallel to the beam axis. The generated magnetic field bends the charged particles according to the magnitude of their charge and transverse momentum. To measure charged particles and photons, the PHENIX central arm tracking (CNT) systems takes advantage of two

Figure 17. Photograph of the half-side view of the FVTX [27].

independent electromagnetic tracking systems: pad chambers (PCs) and the drift chambers (DCs). The PCs and the DCs are installed at the east arm and the west arm separately. The rapidity coverage of the central arm is $0.35 > |\eta|$ with an azimuthal coverage of $70^\circ < \theta < 110^\circ$. Because the rapidity range covers $\eta \sim 0$, the central arm is called mid-rapidity [26, 28].

IV.A DCs

The DCs measure the trajectories and the transverse momenta of charged particles. The two identical DCs located on the east and west arms operate independently. The DC, the innermost detector among the central arm detectors, is positioned 2.0 to 2.4 m away from the center of the beam pipe, which is under the effect of the central magnetic field.

In heavy ion collisions, for high-multiplicity event measurement, the DC meets the requirements of the resolution of a single wire ($< 150 \mu\text{m}$ in the r - ϕ plane) and of

Figure 18. DC frame [28].

double track resolution ($< 1.5 \text{ mm}$), while the efficiency of the single wire is $> 99\%$. The DC is divided into 20 sectors, with one sector covering ϕ with 4.5° separately. Each sector has six different types of wire modules, which are called X1, U1, V1, X2, U2, and V2 from the beam pipe [26].

Figure 19. Wire position within one sector (left). Top view of the wire orientation (right) [28].

IV.B PCs

The PCs give the three-dimensional information of the charged particle trajectories with a precise measurement, especially in the z direction. The PCs are located outside of the PHENIX magnetic field. Therefore, the tracks that connect the inside hitting points with the outside ones should be straight. The tracks measured by the PCs are used for tagging the charged tracks within the events or for measuring track matching for reducing the background from the gamma decays or gamma conversions. The PCs are composed of three detectors: PC1, PC2, and PC3. PC1 is the innermost layer of the PC, and PC3 is at the outer layer. The inside of the

chamber is filled with 50% argon and 50% ethane at atmospheric pressure [26].

IV.C Electromagnetic calorimeter

The electromagnetic calorimeter (EMCal) system specifies the hit position of the charged particles and the energy of photons and electrons. The EMCal system is placed at the outermost layer of the central arm detectors and covers a pseudo-rapidity range of $0.35 > |\eta|$ and azimuthal range of $70^\circ < \theta < 110^\circ$. The EMCal system is composed of two subsystems that are installed in the east and the west central arms separately [26].

V Data Acquisition

The PHENIX data acquisition system (DAQ) collects data in many-particle-collision systems with a high interaction rate. The number of particles produced at PHENIX acceptance varies from a few tracks in small systems to a hundred tracks in the heavy ion collisions. For the collision rate, the PHENIX DAQ system tolerates $p+p$ collisions, which provide up to 500 kHz.

Figure 20 describes the design of the PHENIX DAQ system. The Granule Timing Module (GTM) manages the DAQ system. The Master Timing Module (MTM) receives the RHIC beam clock and sends copies to the global level 1 trigger (GL1) and the GTM. The GL1 combines the data from the GTM, the MTM, the subsystems, and the zero-degree calorimeter (ZDC) and generates the level-1 (LVL1) trigger for delivery to the GTM. The generated signal is temporarily stored in the AMU

while GL1 is actually “triggering” the data. After GL1 decides to trigger the data, the triggering signal delivered to the front-end module (FEM) passes through the GTM. The FEM provides the data packets to the data collection module (DCM), and the produced data packets flow to the event builder (EvB), passing through the partitioner [29].

Figure 20. PHENIX data acquisition system [29].

3 Analysis

I Event Selection

I.A Trigger

The PHENIX Run-15 minimum-bias (MB) data are used to measure v_2 in $p+p$ and $p+Au$ collisions. The MB trigger requires at least one photomultiplier tube (PMT) of the BBC to be fired in the north and south arms, separately. In the $p+Au$ at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV case, the MB event samples cover $\sim 84\%$ of the total inelastic collision cross section simulated by the Monte Carlo Glauber model. The high-multiplicity (central) trigger is based on this MB trigger, with an additional requirement of >35 PMTs in the BBCS firing. This value of 35 corresponds to $\sim 5\%$ of the most central events. For the central trigger event samples, the z -vertex range, which is determined by the hit-time difference of the BBCN and BBCS, is ± 10 cm.

I.B Centrality

The centrality is defined by using the BBC multiplicity distributions. The centrality is defined as the overlap range of the two nuclei, explained by the impact parameter b , shown as the particle multiplicity at an experiment. The left spectrum in Figure 21 shows that the centrality has a uniform distribution for the MB events. The right spectrum shows the relation between the BBCS charge sum in one event and the centrality. The high-multiplicity trigger tends to trigger high-multiplicity events,

which correspond to 0–5% centrality.

Figure 21. (Left) Number of events as a function of the defined centrality using charge multiplicity of the BBC. (Right) BBC south-arm charge sum as a function of centrality.

II Track Selection

II.A DC quality cut

The tracks reconstructed at the central arm are using the track quality cut determined by the DC and the PC1 hit patterns. The DC uses the z -vertex position information decided by the PCs because the PCs are located in the magnetic-free area. If one track has several z -vertex positions that are determined by the PC, then the UV wire in the DC is considered to find the “best match.” Table 2 shows the quality bits of the hit patterns of the PHENIX DC and PC1.

In this analysis, the good track quality cut is chosen as 31 or 63. The best choice

Table 2. Hit pattern quality bits of the PHENIX DC and PC1.

Number	Trigger bit	Condition
0	1	X1 used
1	2	X2 used
2	4	UV found
3	8	UV unique
4	16	PC1 found
5	48	PC1 unique

is 63, for which X1, X2, UV, UV unique and PC1 unique triggered. The second-best choice is 31, wherein PC1 is ambiguous (PC1 found), but the UV and X sectors (X1, X2, UV, UV unique) have hit individually.

II.B PC3 matching cut

The track matching calculation for the outer layer of the central arm is determined by the difference between the trajectory reconstructed by the inner layer detectors such as the DC and the PC1, and the trajectory from extrapolating to the outer layer subsystems such as the EMCal or the PC3. The real-hit candidates are found within a fixed ϕ - z window which is determined by the σ_{matching} . The real hits in the outer layer detectors are decided by the distances of the extrapolated projection

point from the inner layer subsystems. The distribution of difference between the extrapolated position from the inner layer subsystems and the real hits in the outer layer subsystems is nearly a Gaussian distribution with a width of

$$\sigma_{\text{matching}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{detector}}^2 + \frac{\sigma^2}{pT^2}}, \quad (10)$$

where σ_{detector} is the position resolution of the outer layer detector and σ is the resolution of the multiple scattering effect. After the normalizations, in the distance distributions, the mean values are shifted toward zero, and the standard deviation of the signal can be obtained in both azimuthal and longitudinal directions. In this analysis, the PC3 matching cuts are determined in various z_{BBC} and φ bins at the CNT east/west arms and positive/negative charges separately.

II.C FVTX track

The intended rapidity coverage of the FVTX is $1 < |\eta| < 3$. However, this rapidity coverage is distributed by the collision z -vertex position. To eliminate this vertex position effect, a distance of the closest approach cut, DCA_{R} , is developed. The track DCA_{R} is defined by the distance between the track extrapolated position to the vertex xy plane and the vertex (x, y, z) as shown in Figure 22.

DCA_{R} is

$$DCA_{\text{R}} = DCA_x \times \cos \phi + DCA_y \times \sin \phi, \quad (11)$$

where DCA_x and DCA_y are given by

$$DCA_x = x_{\text{trk}} + (\tan \theta \times \cos \phi) \times (z_{\text{trk}} - BBC_z) - X_{\text{Beam}} \quad (12)$$

Figure 22. Schematic view of DCA_R definition.

and

$$DCA_y = y_{\text{trk}} + (\tan \theta \times \sin \phi) \times (z_{\text{trk}} - BBC_z) - Y_{\text{Beam}}, \quad (13)$$

where x_{trk} and y_{trk} are the x and y hit positions, respectively, and X_{Beam} and Y_{Beam} are the beam x and y positions, respectively. The z -vertex is calculated from the BBC, and ϕ and θ are the azimuthal angles of the track extrapolated position.

III Experimental Method for Flow Analysis

A dip structure was found on the near side ($\Delta\phi \sim 0$) of the two-particle correlation functions between the FVTX north and south in the originally produced data (pro.104) that included the VTX hit information on the tracking procedure for FVTX. The dip structure is not found when the FVTX tracks are reconstructed without the VTX hit information, like the PHENIX p +Al Run-15 and the PHENIX d +Au Run-16. Because this dip structure appears in the HIJING simulation with perfect alignment and acceptance. One of the suggested explanations is the largely

different ϕ resolutions between VTX and FVTX. After further investigation, new data sets excluding the VTX hits in the FVTX track reconstruction have been produced. These data sets were produced with pro.106 for $p+p$ and with pro.107 for $p+Au$, and these include only the FVTX track information. Figure 23 shows the dip structure near $\Delta\phi \sim 0$ for both the previous data set and the newly produced data set.

Figure 23. Dip structure found in two-particle correlation functions of FVTX south and FVTX north. The left figure shows the result of the previous data set, which is the FVTX track reconstructed by using VTX hit information. The right figure shows the result of the newly produced data set.

III.A Two-particle correlation with the three-subsystem method

In this analysis, the two-particle correlation with the three-subsystem method is used to quantify v_2 . The two-particle correlation with three-subsystem method

requires three independent subsystems, such as CNT, BBCN, and BBCS, and selection of two tracks from those two independent subsystems, respectively. To find the rapidity-gap and rapidity dependence of v_2 , the results for several three-subsystem combinations are compared. For measuring v_2 using the two-particle correlation with three-subsystem combinations, CNT, BBC(S-N), and FVTX(S-N) are selected to obtain a wide range of rapidity. While it allows to evaluate v_2 for all rapidity range covered by three subsystems, the conventional approach, the event plane method has to exclude the rapidity range where the detector defines the event plane to avoid a self-bias. As the nature of the event plane method, the accuracy of v_2 is directly affected by how well one can define the event plane. This effectively limits the event plane method to be applicable to only high multiplicity circumstances which provides sufficient enough hits/tracks to determine the event plane. From this point of view, the two-particle correlation method has advantage to study the centrality dependence because it avoids to determine the event plane and calculates v_2 from the accumulation of opening azimuthal angle between two tracks.

The schematic view of Figure 24 shows the coverages of each detector. FVTX and BBC are quite close to each other with almost no rapidity gap so that elimination of the near-side jet effect is difficult.

The two-particle correlation method selects one track from each detector, giving it a natural $\Delta\eta$ gap between the selected two tracks. However, because the detector acceptances are limited, the two-particle correlation method provides dif-

Figure 24. Schematic view of the PHENIX detector acceptances.

ferent results depending on the detector acceptance. Therefore, to get v_2 from the two-particle correlation method, the real correlation (two-particle correlation in the same event) and the mixed correlation (correlation of the two particles from different events in the same centrality and z -vertex bins) are needed. After the $\Delta\varphi$ histograms of real and mixed events are obtained, the normalized correlation functions in a certain p_T bin can be obtained by

$$C(\Delta\varphi) = \frac{R(\Delta\varphi)}{M(\Delta\varphi)} \cdot \frac{\int M(\Delta\varphi) \cdot d\varphi}{\int R(\Delta\varphi) \cdot d\varphi}, \quad (14)$$

where R is the real correlation and M is the mixed correlation.

The correlation functions are described by the Fourier cosine expansion function,

$$f(\Delta\varphi) = 1 + \sum c_n \cos(n\Delta\varphi), \quad (15)$$

where each coefficient of the cosine component is c_n . The c_2 values from three different subevent combinations are used to calculate v_2 as

$$v_2^B = \sqrt{\frac{c_2^{B,A} \cdot c_2^{B,C}}{c_2^{A,C}}}, \quad (16)$$

where c_2 is given by

$$c_2^{A,B} = v_2^A \cdot v_2^B, \quad (17)$$

from the relation between the single-particle distribution and the two-particle correlation. The single-particle distribution is then integrated over the trigger angle,

$$\frac{dN^{\text{ta}}}{d\Delta\phi} = \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi^{\text{t}} \frac{dN^{\text{t}}}{d\phi^{\text{t}}} \frac{dN^{\text{a}}}{d\phi^{\text{a}}}, \quad (18)$$

where N^{ta} is the number of pairs of tracks, $\Delta\phi$ is $\phi^{\text{a}} - \phi^{\text{t}}$, and N^{t} and N^{a} are the numbers of trigger and associated particles, respectively.

Therefore,

$$\frac{dN^{\text{ta}}}{d\Delta\phi} \propto \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi^{\text{t}} \left\{ 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1} v_k^{\text{t}} \cos k(\phi^{\text{t}} - \Psi_k) \right\} \left\{ 1 + 2 \sum_{l=1} v_l^{\text{a}} \cos l(\phi^{\text{a}} - \Psi_l) \right\} \quad (19)$$

and only the $k = l$ term survives:

$$\frac{dN^{\text{ta}}}{d\Delta\phi} \propto \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi^{\text{t}} \left\{ 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1} v_k^{\text{t}} v_k^{\text{a}} \cos k(\Delta\phi) \right\}. \quad (20)$$

As a result,

$$\frac{dN^{\text{ta}}}{d\Delta\phi} = b_0 \left\{ 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1} v_k^{\text{t}} v_k^{\text{a}} \cos k(\Delta\phi) \right\} \quad (21)$$

is obtained.

IV Nonflow Estimation

In contrast to the heavy ion collision cases, the nonflow effect is dominant even in high-multiplicity (central) events in small systems. To examine the effect from the nonflow, all combinations made by CNT, BBC(S-N), and FVTX(S-N) are considered. To study nonflow behavior in each detector combination, $|c_2/c_1|$ of the

two-particle correlations is evaluated as a function of the centrality for all detector combinations in Figure 25. The value of $|c_2/c_1|$ gives the relative size of the ridge-like structure with respect to the magnitude of a bulk property of the system [30]. This $|c_2/c_1|$ measurement shows strong centrality dependencies. As centrality goes toward the peripheral, $|c_2/c_1|$ becomes smaller.

In Figure 25, the black symbols represent the centrality dependence of the $p+Au$ results and the red dashed lines represent $|c_2/c_1|$ calculated in $p+p$ MB events at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. Generally the $p+p$ MB results shows similarity with $p+Au$ peripheral collision results. This implies the flow component of $p+Au$ peripheral is as negligibly small as $p+p$ MB, as expected from its low multiplicity. As can be commonly seen as a trend in all panels, $|c_2/c_1|$ decreases as a function of centrality and asymptotically approaches some constant. This constant is an indication of the fraction of nonflow component because the constant values are well reproduced when the same analysis is applied to the MB samples of $p+p$ collisions where no flow effect is anticipated (as it is driven by a pure nonflow effect). Moreover, the $|c_2/c_1|$ values in $p+p$ collisions represent the nonflow effect's dependence on the detector combinations (or $\Delta\eta$) in small systems. The inconsistency of $|c_2/c_1|$ values between $p+Au$ peripheral and minimum-bias $p+p$ implies there are some effect which comes from the multiplicity effect. Because BBCS-FVTS is a combination of south and south, $p+Au$ BBCS-FVTS combination has a larger multiplicity than that of $p+p$. The multiplicity is approximately converted to the size of the QGP, the discrepancy

between the $|c_2/c_1|$ in p +Au and that of p + p can be the evidence of flow generated in p +Au.

Figure 25. $|c_2/c_1|$ as a function of centrality at p +Au $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV in different detector combinations. The red dashed line shows p + p $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV $|c_2/c_1|$ of MB.

Figure 26 shows $|c_2/c_1|$ as a function of p_T for three kinds of detector combinations. From left to right, CNT-BBCS, CNT-FVTN, and CNT-FVTS two-particle correlation results are shown, respectively. As shown in Figure 25, there is a tendency that the central collision has the largest $|c_2/c_1|$ and the peripheral collision has the smallest $|c_2/c_1|$. Measurement of $|c_2/c_1|$ implies that one can derive the centrality dependence of c_2 by measuring the relative size of c_2 with respect to c_1 in the function of p_T .

Figure 26. $|c_2/c_1|$ as a function of p_T at $p+Au$ $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV in different detector combinations.

IV.A Reference fit method

For estimation of the nonflow effect, the reference fit method proposed by the Tsukuba group is discussed and compared with the c_1 scaling method, which is a particular case of the reference fit method [31]. The reference fit method is one experimental approach used to extract the flow effect by using the central event correlation histogram and subtracting the peripheral event correlation histogram. By doing this, the difference between the high-multiplicity correlation function and the low-multiplicity correlation function is obtained. The reference fit method is different from the template fit method, which was designed by the CMS collaboration, in the way it uses the flow yield estimations. The template fit method estimates the yield of the flow and multiplies the yield ratio of the flow and total yield to the measured c_n . In contrast, in the reference fit method one assumes that an accurate flow yield estimation is impossible. Therefore, the reference fit method explains the determined c_2 on top of the total yield, while the template fit method explains

the determined c_2 at the level of the estimated flow yield. Using the reference fit method gives a smaller size for c_2 compared to that obtained by using the template fit method. This philosophical difference between two methods results in the reproducibility of the original c_1 and c_2 values out of the fitting process. The reference fit demonstrated more stable reproducibility within the cases examined compared to that of the template fit. The case test will be discussed in Section IV.C using a toy Monte Carlo [32].

In central collisions (high-multiplicity events), the correlation histogram is

$$C_{\text{high}}(\Delta\varphi) = 1 + \Sigma 2a_n \cos n\phi. \quad (22)$$

The correlation histogram of the ridge component is

$$C_{\text{ridge}}(\Delta\varphi) = 1 + \Sigma_{n=2} 2c_n \cos n\phi, \quad (23)$$

where c_n is the result of reference fit method.

The correlation histogram for peripheral collisions (low-multiplicity events) is

$$C_{\text{low}}(\Delta\varphi) = C_{\text{hard}}(\Delta\varphi) + C_{\text{soft}}(\Delta\varphi), \quad (24)$$

when the hard component (nonflow component) of low-multiplicity correlation function is

$$C_{\text{hard}} = H[1 + \Sigma 2h_n \cos n\Delta\varphi] \quad (25)$$

and the soft component (flow component) of low-multiplicity correlation function is

$$C_{\text{soft}} = G_0[1 + \Sigma 2c_n^0 \cos n\Delta\varphi] \quad (26)$$

respectively, while G_0 and H are the level of soft and hard component, respectively.

The reference fit function is

$$F(\Delta\varphi) = a + bC_{\text{low}}(\Delta\varphi), \quad (27)$$

where a and b are free parameters. From the fitting procedure, $F(\Delta\varphi)$ is also normalized to 1. Therefore, the relationship between a and b satisfies $a + b = 1$.

The fitting histogram C_{ref} that will apply to the central correlation histogram is

$$C_{\text{ref}}(\Delta\varphi) = F(\Delta\varphi) + C_{\text{ridge}}(\Delta\varphi) + D \quad (28)$$

where D is a free parameter.

If the $C_{\text{ref}}(\Delta\varphi)$ explains $C_{\text{high}}(\Delta\varphi)$ successfully, we have

$$C_{\text{ref}}(\Delta\varphi) = C_{\text{ridge}}(\Delta\varphi) + F(\Delta\varphi) + D = C_{\text{high}}(\Delta\varphi) \quad (29)$$

The fitting result of C_{ref} (C_{high}) should be

$$2a_n \cos n\phi = (a - bH - bG_0 + D) + bH\Sigma 2h_n \cos n\phi + bG_0\Sigma 2c_n^0 \cos n\phi + 2c_n \cos n\phi. \quad (30)$$

Therefore, c_n is

$$c_n = a_n - b(Hh_n + G_0c_n^0). \quad (31)$$

IV.B c_1 scaling method

Figure 27 shows c_1 , c_2 , and $|c_2/c_1|$ as a function of centrality for various detector combinations, respectively. The clear centrality dependence in $|c_2/c_1|$ indicates the

different nonflow contribution for different three-subsystem combinations. In contrast, the c_2 value does not show a strong centrality dependence. In the previous PHENIX results, the nonflow contribution has been estimated with c_2 in $p+p$ collisions scaled by the charge ratio at the BBCS between $p+p$ and $p+Au$ collisions. Based on the assumption of the reference fit to estimate the nonflow contribution in c_2 by subtracting the correlation function in $p+p$ or peripheral collisions, $p+Au$ scaled with the c_1 ratio,

$$c_2^{scaled} = c_2^{pAu} - (c_1^{pAu}/c_1^{pp}) \times c_2^{pp}, \quad (32)$$

can be derived.

Because of the three-subsystem combinations,

$$v_2^{baseline} = \sqrt{c_2^{scaled,A} * c_2^{scaled,B} / c_2^{scaled,C}}, \quad (33)$$

where A , B , and C are the detector combinations, respectively.

Figure 27. c_1 (top), c_2 (middle), and $|c_2/c_1|$ (bottom) as a function centrality with various detector combinations in $p+Au$ collisions.

By using this procedure, the different scaling factors for the dedicated detector combinations ($\Delta\eta$) can be applied. Figure 28 shows a comparison between c_2 of p +Au collisions (green), c_2 of p + p collisions scaled by the BBCS charge ratio (black), and the c_1 ratio (red) calculated from the CNT-BBCS combinations (top), CNT-FVTS combinations (middle), and BBCS-FVTS combinations (bottom), respectively. The CNT-BBCS correlation with c_2 scaled by Q_{BBCS} is almost half the size of that with c_2 scaled by c_1 . However, for the CNT-FVTS correlation, which is shown in the middle plot of Figure 28, the c_1 scaling estimates much larger nonflow contributions and stronger p_T dependence than the BBC charge scaling method. The difference between the green curves and the red curves implies the flow behavior estimated by the c_1 scaling method. The c_1 scaling method also shows a $\Delta\eta$ dependence of the two-particle correlations, so the difference between the green and red curves for the CNT-BBCS combination is larger compared to that for the CNT-FVTS combination.

Figure 29 shows a comparison between the previous published result [24] and that from this analysis for v_2 at the CNT as a function of p_T . The lower limits of the systematic uncertainties correspond to the nonflow estimation with different assumptions. The results show a largely different estimation of nonflow contribution when the c_1 scaling method is used. For this thesis, except for Figure 29 v_2 is calculated without systematic uncertainty which comes from nonflow estimation.

Figure 28. c_2 comparisons between (black) $p+p$ c_2 , which is scaled by the BBCS charge sum ratio, between $p+p$ MB and $p+Au$ 0–5%. (Red) $p+p$ c_2 , which is scaled by c_1^{p+Au} 0–5% and c_1^{p+MB} . (Green) c_2 $p+Au$ 0–5%. (Left) CNT-BBCS. (Right) CNT-FVTS. (Bottom) BBBS-FVTS.

Figure 29. v_2 in the most central event (0–5%) comparison (black) published result with event-plane method with systematic error comes from BBC charge scaling and (red) new result with two particle correlation method with systematic error comes from c_1 scaling method.

IV.C Toy Monte Carlo simulation of the reference fit method

The closure test of the toy Monte Carlo (MC) simulations of the reference fit method is presented in this section. The MC test is designed to quantify the reproduced c_2^{sub} , which is the result of the subtraction method. In this test, the four combinations of c_1 and c_2 are tested for proof of principle, and the yield of flow is always half of total yield at the high multiplicity correlation function. The c_1^{jet} and the c_2^{jet} represent c_1 and c_2 component of the jet, respectively. Likewise, c_1^{flow} and the c_2^{flow} represent c_1 and c_2 component of the flow, respectively. In all cases resulting c_2^{temp} , which is the result of template fit method, has larger value compared to value of c_2^{ref} , which is the result of the reference fit method, because the reference fit method always explains c_2^{ref} at the level of total yield. The template fit result c_2^{temp} is at the level of estimated flow yield, the size of c_2^{temp} became larger compared to c_2^{ref} .

Figure 30 shows that the most simple case of the c_1 and the c_2 combinations; the jet only has nonzero c_1 while the flow only has nonzero c_2 . Panel (a) shows the jet shape with normalized to 1. Likewise, panel (b) shows the flow shape with normalized to 1. Panels (c) and (d) show the peripheral histogram and the central histogram, respectively. Panel (e) shows the central histogram and the reproduced c_2 with emphasized scales. In this case, the reference fit method can reproduce the c_2 .

Figure 30. Simulation result of the nonflow, consisting of c_1 ; the flow consists of c_2 .

Figure 31 shows that the jet has nonzero c_1^{jet} and c_2^{jet} while the flow only has the c_2^{flow} . Because c_2 is the indicator of the flow component, whatever comes from the c_2^{jet} , resulting c_2^{sub} considered as flow. The subtracted c_2^{ref} has a half value of c_2^{flow} because it is reflected yield ratio between the flow and total at the high-multiplicity correlation function. As discussed in the previous section, the reference fit method does not use the flow yield. Therefore, the misled flow yield owing to the nonzero c_2/c_1 of the jet is not concerned by the reference fit method.

Figure 31. Toy MC simulation result of the nonflow containing not only c_1 but also c_2 .

Even there is a non zero c_2^{jet} component, the flow fraction is mostly determined by the c_1^{jet} in the high multiplicity event. Therefore, this case gives proper subtraction

Figure 32. Scanning result of Toy MC simulation of the reproduced $c_2^{\text{sub}}/c_2^{\text{flow}}$ as a function of the given $c_2^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$.

baseline to the result of the template fit method. Figure 32 shows the scan result of c_2^{sub} as a function of $c_1^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$. Both template fit and reference fit results give stable c_2^{sub} while scanning the varied $c_1^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$. Because template fit successfully estimate flow yield, result reproduces c_2^{flow} reasonably.

However, if the flow contains c_1^{flow} and c_2^{flow} at the same time, the template fit fails to estimate exact flow yield level because flow yield is estimated using difference between c_1^{jet} and c_1^{flow} as shown in Figure 33. Therefore, because c_2^{temp} is calculated on the level of the estimated yield of flow, the result of the template fit can be misguided as a function of the ratio between c_1^{flow} and c_1^{jet} . Figure 34 shows the result of ratio between reproduced c_2^{sub} and true c_2^{flow} . Because the reference fit method calculates c_2^{ref} on the top of the total yield level, c_2^{ref} value set to $Y^{\text{flow}}/Y^{\text{high}}$. In contrast, the template fit method calculates c_2^{temp} at the level of estimated flow yield, the final result of template fit method has dependence on $c_2^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$.

Figure 33. Simulation result of the flow containing not only c_1^{flow} but also c_2^{flow} .

Figure 33 and Figure 34 show the case of jet for c_1^{jet} and c_2^{jet} , while flow has c_2^{flow}

Figure 34. Scanning result of Toy MC simulation of the reproduced c_2 as a function of the given $c_1^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$ when c_2^{jet} is zero.

only. If the jet contains c_1^{jet} and c_2^{jet} at the same time, template fit result vary while the $c_1^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$ change. However, the reference fit result has stable value. Like the previous case, because reference fit method estimated flow at the level of total yield, the reproduced $c_2^{\text{ref}}/c_2^{\text{flow}}$ is 0.5 because of the ratio between flow and total yield of high multiplicity correlation function. In contrast, the template fit method fails to estimate flow yield in this case, resulting c_2^{temp} has dependency on the $c_1^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$, which is the factor of estimates nonflow level.

Figure 35. Simulation result of the nonflow and the flow, containing not only c_1 but also c_2 , respectively.

Figure 35 and 36 show the case of jet and flow with nonzero c_1 and c_2 , respectively. In this case both reference and template fit method results are affected from nonzero c_1^{flow} . However, the reference fit results, $c_2^{\text{ref}}/c_2^{\text{flow}}$, show smaller values of slope as a function of $c_2^{\text{jet}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$.

Figure 37 shows an example results of the real data in $p+\text{Au}$ $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. Left spectrum shows the template fit results as a blue dashed line, and right spectrum shows the reference fit results as a red data points. Like what is observed in the simulations, the size of amplitude of c_2^{ref} and c_2^{temp} is almost same. The difference between the resulting values comes from the yield level which is expanded each c_2^{ref}

and c_2^{temp} . The left figure shows the template fit method result, and as it shows the resulting c_2^{temp} explains at the level of yellow line, which is not the same level of total yield. However, the right figure shows the reference fit result and it explains at the level of total yield. Therefore the size of c_2^{ref} became smaller compared to c_2^{temp} , as the toy MC simulation results shown.

Figure 36. Simulation result of reproduced c_2 as a function of the given $c_2^{\text{flow}}/c_1^{\text{jet}}$.

Figure 37. Data result of FVTX north and south correlation histogram. (Left) The open circles give a reference histogram and in this figure it is $p+Au$ $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV 60–84%. The solid circles are the $p+Au$ 0–5% two-particle correlation histogram. The blue line is the result of c_2 being subtracted. (Right) Red data points are the result of a reference fit. The blue solid line is the fit result of the subtracted value.

V Systematic Uncertainty

The systematic error is the uncertainty which is caused by the measurement circumstances like the limitation of the detector resolution, or selection criteria of each tracks or events. To measure the systematic uncertainty with reduced statistical fluctuations of the v_2 ratio is

$$R_{v_2} = \frac{\sum_i R_{v_2,i} \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_{stat,i}^2}}{\sum_i \frac{1}{\sigma_{stat,i}^2}},$$

where $R_{v_2,i}$ is the ratio of each histogram bins, and $\sigma_{stat,i}$ is the statistical uncertainty of each histogram bin. By doing this, the size of systematic error from the large statistics can be weighted summed to the total systematic error. Figure 38, Figure 39, Figure 39, Figure 42 and Figure 43 show the averaged ratio of the systematic uncertainty which is plotted as a dashed line. Because the ratio in each bin is consistent within statistical uncertainties, the averaged ratio is assigned to all the histogram bins within one rapidity coverage at the same three-subsystem combination. In this section, the v_2 as a function of p_T results are shown to describe the systematic uncertainty as an brief example. All the systematic uncertainty is tabulated in Table A.1 for the p_T dependence study, and Table A.2, Table A.3, and Table A.4 for the rapidity study.

V.A PC3 matching cut

The CNT tracks are selected within 2σ range of PC3 matching cut. By comparing results between the 2σ and 3σ cut, the v_2 systematic uncertainty is assigned. Fig-

Figure 38 shows the comparison of the v_2 as a function of p_T between the 2σ cut result and the 3σ cut result in different centrality bins. The black curves represent the 2σ cut results, while the red curves represent the 3σ cut results. The results with 3σ PC3 matching cuts are consistent with the results with 2σ PC3 matching cuts within the statistical uncertainties.

Figure 38. Variation of v_2 with 2σ or 3σ PC3 matching cut for the systematic study of 200-GeV p +Au collisions.

V.B CNT E–W difference

The CNT east and west arm difference effect is strongly related to the tilted beam angle of the asymmetry collision system like p +Au, d +Au, or ^3He +Au. However the two-particle correlation method uses the mixed event correlation for the v_2 calculation, the beam angle effect shows smaller than the event plane calculation. Figure 39 and Figure 40 show the weighted sum result of this beam angle effect.

Figure 39. v_2 comparison using the whole range of CNT acceptance and only a select east area.

The black curves represent the total acceptance, while the red curves represent

Figure 40. v_2 comparison using the whole range of CNT acceptance and only a select west area.

the result of the CNT east and the CNT west tracks selection. The v_2 measurements of CNT east and CNT west selections give the consistent results to the total acceptance result within the statistical uncertainties.

V.C Double interaction effect

The systematic uncertainty can be also caused by the double interaction tagger which is used for the multi-vertex collisions event tagging. The PHENIX can reconstruct the several kinds of vertices using the various systems. The double interaction tagger shows as the charge fraction (f) around the timing peak, which is calculated by the BBC. The variation with a tighter cut (>0.95) and a looser cut (>0.85) are calculated, respectively, for the v_2 as a function of the p_T measurement, as shown in Figure 42 and Figure 43, respectively. For the η dependence measurement, the calculation cut is used with $f > 0.95$ to have tighter sort out of the double interactions within the high multiplicity events.

Figure 41. Distribution of charge fraction around the timing peak in BBCS of one run (432745) in 200 GeV p +Au collisions.

Figure 42. Variation of v_2 with a looser BBC charge fraction cut (>0.85) for a systematic study in 200-GeV p +Au collisions.

Figure 43. Variation of v_2 with a tighter BBC charge fraction cut (>0.95) for a systematic study in 200-GeV p +Au 200 collisions.

4 Results and Discussion

I Charged Hadron v_2 at Mid-rapidity

v_2 measured by the charged hadrons at the mid-rapidity with the centrality dependence is shown in Figure 44. From 0% to 84%, the centrality changes from the central collision to the peripheral collision. The centrality bins for the four spectra in Figure 44 are defined by 0%–5%, 5%–30%, 30%–60%, and 60%–84%, respectively. The black data points are the new measurements from the two-particle correlation method, and the red data points are the v_2 published results at the p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV 0%–5% centrality, respectively. The top left spectrum shows the comparison results of the two-particle correlation method and the event-plane method. The two-particle correlation method successfully reproduces the published data within the statistical uncertainty. The different size of the systematic uncertainty between the event-plane method and the two-particle correlation method is due to the way of nonflow estimation. The new measurement does not estimate the systematic uncertainty in respect of the nonflow effect.

The published data are from the event-plane method which uses the event-plane determined by the FVTX south hits distribution, with the event-plane resolution calculated by the three subsystems; FVTX south, BBC south, and CNT. The black circled points are the results of the two-particle correlation method with the same three subsystems as for the case of the event-plane method; FVTX south, BBC

Figure 44. The v_2 for PHENIX p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV as a function of p_T with centrality dependence. From left top, the centrality moves to the peripheral collision.

south and CNT, to reproduce the v_2 measurement of the event-plane method. Both the reproduced publish data and the new measurement of the centrality dependence of the v_2 as a function of p_T are shown in Figure 44. From the v_2 study with extended to the centrality dependency, one can conclude the v_2 does not provide strong centrality dependence as expected from the QGP formation. The v_2 value gets larger while the collision center moves to the peripheral. The result of v_2 as a

function of p_T with centrality dependence shows the measured v_2 behaves such that it is strongly affected by the nonflow effect, which is not originated from the QGP.

The measured v_2 as a function of p_T with centrality dependence shows the opposite trend to the systematic behavior which can predict from Figure 25, which shows the clear and strong dependence of the c_2/c_1 as a function of the centrality. The v_2 as a function of p_T in the p +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV does not provide any clear systematic behavior to the centrality. Moreover, v_2 has higher value in peripheral collisions, unlike what one can predict from Figure 25. The measured v_2 shows different trend compared to what one can predict from the QGP origin. From the v_2 measurement, the considerable effect of the nonflow is anticipated, so the more detailed study about the nonflow effect becomes essential.

II Charged Hadron v_2 over a Wide-Rapidity Range

II.A Two-particle correlation

The corrected p_T is applied to the calculation of v_2 as a function of the rapidity because each detector acceptance has a different ability of the p_T measurement. The correction factors for p_T of each detector are calculated by using AMPT and the single-particle generator which both use the GEANT simulations for the d +Au, $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV system at the rapidity of $\eta < 3$ for the former and at the rapidity of $4 > \eta > 3$ for the latter. The single-particle event generator creates events following phenomenological p_T and rapidity distributions. Detector response of gen-

erated events were simulated using PISA, which is the GEANT model developed for PHENIX detectors. The resulting v_2^{output} values including simulated detector response are compared with the original v_2^{input} values (input v_2 of the event generators). The correction factor R is given by

$$R = \frac{v_2^{\text{input}}}{v_2^{\text{output}}}. \quad (34)$$

Figure 45 shows the criteria of the forward–backward, the backward–backward, and the forward–forward combinations. The forward–backward combination adopts three-subsystem combinations which consists of one forward-rapidity detector and one backward-rapidity detector, and the CNT. The backward–backward combination takes advantage of the identical three-subsystem combination, but its components are different; two backward-rapidity detectors and CNT, or two backward-rapidity detectors and one forward-rapidity detector. Likewise, the forward–forward combination means three-subsystem combinations which are composed of two forward-rapidity detectors and CNT, or two forward-rapidity detectors and one backward-rapidity detector.

Figure 45. Detector selection classification criteria. From left to right, the CNT forward-backward, the backward-backward, and the forward-forward combinations are shown, respectively. The solid line means that a subsystem is always included. The dashed line indicates that a subsystem is optional.

Figure 46 shows the v_2 values as a function of the centrality. The v_2 values are compared for various three subsystems which are selected among the CNT, the FVTX south, the FVTX north, the BBC south, and the BBC north. The black points represent the combinations of the forward–backward combinations and show the highest v_2 at the mid-rapidity. The red and blue points represent the combinations of the backward–backward (BBCS + FVTXS combinations with the mid or the forward rapidity) and the forward–forward (BBCN + FVTXN combinations with the mid or the backward rapidity), respectively. The backward–backward shows the largest v_2 at the rapidity coverage of the FVTX south, while the forward–forward shows the largest v_2 at the FVTX north.

The same-arm combinations (backward–backward, or forward–forward combinations) give the enhanced v_2 at the rapidity range of the FVTX. In contrast, the different-arm combinations (CNT with forward–backward combinations) show the largest v_2 at mid-rapidity. Figure 47 are only the results of the different-arm combinations, which show the largest v_2 at the mid-rapidity. Likewise, Figure 48 and Figure 49 show only the backward–backward combinations and forward–forward combinations, respectively. The v_2 enhancement at the FVTX rapidity range is clearly shown in the same-arm combinations.

Figure 46. v_2 as a function of centrality with rapidity dependence is calculated by using the two-particle correlation method with three-subsystem combinations. Data points in several colors, which are calculated by using the three-subsystem combinations, represent the combination of forward-backward combination with mid-rapidity (black), backward-backward combination with mid- or forward rapidity (red), and forward-forward combination with mid- or backward rapidity (blue), respectively. Systematic uncertainties are calculated by pc3 matching, BBC multi-vertex, and CNT east-west differences of each three-subsystem combination, separately.

Figure 47. v_2 as a function of η with centrality dependence and a three-subsystem combination with forward ($\eta > 0$), backward ($\eta < 0$), and mid-rapidity.

Figure 48. v_2 as a function of η with centrality dependence and three-subsystem combinations with backward ($\eta < 0$)–backward and mid- or forward rapidity.

Figure 49. v_2 as a function of η with centrality dependence and three-subsystem combinations with forward ($\eta > 0$)–forward and mid- or backward rapidity.

Because all of the PHENIX experiments associated with small system collisions are the asymmetric collisions except for the $p+p$ collision, the multiplicities at the forward and the backward is different from each other. According to the PHENIX experiment system, the targets (heavy ions) are guided into the collision vertex from the north while the projectiles (proton, deuteron, and ^3He) are accelerated onto the collision vertex from the south. As a result, the south arm refers to the target-going side (or the Au-going side at $p+\text{Au}$) and the north arm refers to the projectile-going side (or the p-going side).

The amplified v_2 at the forward–forward or the backward–backward combination can be explained by a small rapidity gap. As shown in Figure 45, it is hard to decide a sufficient rapidity gap that can eliminate the nearside jet effect if the two subsystems are placed at the same arm. Because the measured v_2 values of the three subsystems are obtained from Equation 16, the middle-located subsystem among the three subsystems are always suffered from the large c_2 which comes from the small rapidity gap. In the case of the identical arm combination, the enhancement effect appears large at the FVTX coverage.

For instance, the backward–backward combination with the CNT gives v_2 at the FVTX south,

$$v_2^{FVTXS} = \sqrt{\frac{c_2^{BBCS-FVTXS} \times c_2^{FVTXS-CNT}}{c_2^{BBCS-CNT}}}. \quad (35)$$

Therefore, the non-eliminated near-side jet effect remains at the v_2^{FVTXS} , because the jet-originated enlarged $c_2^{BBCS-FVTXS}$ is not canceled out by $c_2^{BBCS-CNT}$ and

$c_2^{FVTXS-CNT}$.

The results of v_2 for small systems, which were already published by the PHENIX experiments [24, 23, 42], are measured by the event-plane method using backward-backward combination due to the lack of the forward multiplicity. However, v_2 derived from the backward-backward combinations shows biased information owing to the nonflow effect, which is dominated at the backward rapidity of the FVTX coverage.

Another point is that the smallest multiplicity combination, which is the forward-forward combination, gives the larger v_2 at the FVTX coverage. The backward-backward combination provides the larger v_2 at the backward FVTX rapidity. Likewise, the forward-forward combination provides the larger v_2 at the forward rapidity, while the forward-backward combination measured v_2 of the backward rapidity gives the smallest v_2 among the three kinds of the three-subsystem combinations. An amplified effect of this combination dependence is more dominant at the north arm (p-going side, lower multiplicity) than at the south arm. Because the nonflow is suppressed by the inverse-weight of the particle multiplicity, one can expect the amplified v_2 at the FVTX north coverage is due to the low multiplicity at the north arm. However, such a comparison measurement of v_2 obtained from the forward-forward does not necessarily mean that the flow is larger (or even smaller) at the north arm than at the south arm.

In all rapidity ranges, v_2 does not show any systematic behavior to the centrality.

However, the CMS and the ATLAS studies demonstrate the ridge structure is more dominant in the high-multiplicity event(central event). In addition, a study of relative c_2 , which is normalized by c_2 as shown in Figure 25, proves that an increasing or a steady trend of v_2 at lower multiplicity can be explained by the nonflow effect.

II.B Nonflow subtraction

Figure 50 shows the results of the reference fit method. The most peripheral events are used as a non-flow-dominant effect. In many three-subsystem combinations, the clear centrality dependence appears after the nonflow subtraction using the reference fit method. From the measurement of the v_2^{ref} , which indicates the v_2 results of the reference fit method, one can conclude v_2^{ref} in many of the three-subsystem combinations show systematic trends with respect to the centrality(multiplicity). The multiplicity dependence of v_2 can be a strong evidence of the QGP. Therefore, the centrality dependence of the v_2^{ref} may be the evidence of the measured v_2 at the small system contains the QGP flow. However, the centrality dependence does not show in all of the three-subsystems results. Moreover, the results are not consistent with each other. As a consequence, the reference fit results imply necessity of deeper understanding about the small systems nonflow behavior.

Figure 50. v_2 as a function of centrality with rapidity dependence calculated by using the reference fit method. Data points in several colors, which are calculated by using the three-subsystem combinations, represent the combination of forward–backward with mid-rapidity (black), backward–backward combination with mid- or forward rapidity (red), and forward–forward combination with mid- or backward rapidity (blue), respectively. Systematic uncertainties are calculated by using pc3 matching, BBC multi-vertex, and CNT east–west differences of each three-subsystem combination, separately.

III $p+p$ Minimum Bias Results

III.A Charged hadron v_2 at mid-rapidity

Figure 51 shows the measured v_2 as a function of p_T for the $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV in the mid-rapidity region. v_2 shows a clear dependence to the three-subsystem combination. It is observed that v_2 of the same arm combination is significantly different from that of the different arm combination in the $p+p$ collision. In $p+p$ collisions, the different arm combination (forward–backward) gives a high value of v_2 compared to the same arm combination at the mid-rapidity, which corresponds to v_2 measurement obtained from $p+Au$ collisions.

III.B Charged hadron v_2 at wide-rapidity range

To study the non-flow-dominant effect of the measured v_2 as a function of the η , the MB event samples of the $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV are examined. Like the case of $p+Au$ collisions, the measured v_2 is improved by the p_T correction factor which eliminates the p_T measure dependence of the detector. The $p+Au$ results demonstrate that the amplified v_2 is found at the FVTX coverages for the same arm combinations, while v_2 is the largest at the mid-rapidity for the different arm combination. The same arm combination v_2 as a function of rapidity for $p+p$ collisions shows the clear non-flow-dominant effect as discussed in the $p+Au$ case. Because $p+p$ is the symmetric collision, the multiplicities of the forward and the backward are similar so that the effect of the nonflow suppression on the north and

Figure 51. Measured v_2 as a function of p_T at mid-rapidity for the $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV for various three-subsystem combinations using the two-particle correlation method. These v_2 results contain nonflow effects.

the south is identical.

Figure 52. $p+p$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV measured v_2 as a function of centrality with rapidity dependence calculated by using the two-particle correlation method with three-subsystem combinations. Data points calculated from each three-subsystem combination and each color represent the combination of forward-backward with mid-rapidity (black), backward-backward combination with mid- or forward rapidity (red), and forward-forward combination with mid- or backward rapidity (blue), respectively. Systematic uncertainties are calculated by using pc3 matching, BBC multi-vertex, and CNT east-west differences of each three-subsystem combination, separately.

5 Conclusion

The multiplicity, $\Delta\eta$, and rapidity dependencies of v_2 are studied by using the two-particle correlation method in $p+p$ and $p+\text{Au}$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV. The resulting v_2 shows strong dependency in $\Delta\eta$. Substantial enhancement in v_2 is found in the range of FVTX ($1 < |\eta| < 3$) particularly for the three-subsystem combinations of forward–forward or backward–backward combinations with mid-rapidity. This is likely to be caused by the substantial nonflow contribution from the insufficient rapidity gap. However, when a sufficient size of $\Delta\eta$ is secured by using the different arm combinations (forward–backward combinations), v_2 has its largest value at mid-rapidity. The enhanced v_2 is also found at the lower multiplicity events at the small collision systems. This can be explained by the anti-proportional correlation between nonflow suppression and the number of total particles. Consequentially, the enhanced v_2 at the FVTX coverage is the evidence of the strong nonflow effect owing to the small rapidity gap between the two particles, and this does not correspond to how QGP behaves.

The study of the $|c_2/c_1|$ ratio as a function of multiplicity allows us to estimate nonflow fraction in the two-particle correlation observables without background subtraction procedures. The study demonstrated strong centrality dependence in the $|c_2/c_1|$ for various detector combinations. The trend was common to all combinations, i.e., the $|c_2/c_1|$ becomes smaller as the multiplicity gets lower. Moreover, the

MB data samples of the $p+p$ results are consistent with $p+Au$ peripheral events indicating no flow signal in the present peripheral event samples. Relatively large fraction of the nonflow effect even in the most central $|c_2/c_1|$ supports the aforementioned indication which is nonflow effect dominates v_2 observables in $p+Au$. In contrast to the results of v_2 as a function of rapidity, the $|c_2/c_1|$ results show relevant trends with the expectations of the QGP behaviors.

Unlike the $|c_2/c_1|$ ratio study, the centrality dependence of the v_2 without the background subtraction is found to be difficult to address the systematic behavior expected from the flow effect. The simple measurement of the v_2 shows the non-systematic behavior as a function of the centrality, due to the nonflow dominance at the peripheral events compared to the central events. Regardless of the rapidity gap, observed v_2 of any three subsystem combinations did not show the centrality dependence expected from the flow effect. This is an indication of the nonflow domination in v_2 for small systems.

By the reference fit method which is invented to subtract the nonflow effect, it is available to evaluate the flow behaviors like the trend of $|c_2/c_1|$ results. In many three-subsystem combinations, the results of the reference fit method clearly show the v_2 centrality dependence. In spite of there are some exceptions that behave differently from others, the result of the subtraction showed the centrality dependence as expected from the flow effect for the majority of combinations evaluated in this analysis. Therefore, although further investigation of the subtraction is needed, the

extracted v_2 is less biased than previous analysis, which helps to understand QGP at the small system.

Appendix A

Tables for systematic uncertainties

Table A.1. Total systematic uncertainty estimation

Centrality	PC3 matching	DCA_R	Multicollision	West-east	Total
0%–5%	2%	1%	2%	4%	6%
5%–30%	4%	1%	2%	12%	13%
30%–60%	3%	2%	3%	14%	15%
60%–84%	5%	2%	5%	12%	15%

Table A.2. Total systematic uncertainty estimation (%)

Combination	System	Multi	CNT	PC3	ZVTX	Sum
CNTBBCNBBCS	BBCS	0.21	14.42	0.72	2.01	14.58
CNTFVTNBBCS	BBCS	1.35	12.44	1.81	0.89	12.68
BBCNFVTSBBCS	BBCS	3.81	0.65	1.25	2.76	4.84
CNTFVTSBBCS	BBCS	1.16	11.18	1.53	0.25	11.35
BBCNFVTNBBCS	BBCS	3.93	1.46	1.03	2.53	5
CNTBBCNFVTS	FVTS	2.7	37.30	2.87	1.27	37.52
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTS	3.88	13.79	2.25	0.28	14.5
BBCNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	3.25	2.19	1.55	3.74	5.63
CNTFVTSBBCS	FVTS	0.75	24.57	2.15	0.78	24.68
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	3.4	2.50	1.77	0.72	4.64
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTS	1.96	1.74	1.23	2.91	4.1
CNTBBCNFVTS	FVTS	3.71	24.28	2.33	0.62	24.69
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTS	0.19	2.34	0.37	0.13	2.38
BBCNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	3.66	0.08	0.06	1.66	4.02
CNTFVTSBBCS	FVTS	0.79	9.76	1.21	0.58	9.88
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	0.17	0.11	0.08	0.48	0.52
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTS	0.42	1.46	1.03	0.03	1.83

Table A.3. Total systematic uncertainty estimation (%)

Combination	System	Multi	CNT	PC3	ZVTX	Sum
CNTBBCNFVTS	FVTS	3.81	24.95	3.01	0.01	25.42
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTS	0.44	2.93	0.1	0.6	3.02
BBCNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	4.91	1.39	0.98	2.48	5.76
CNTFVTSBBCS	FVTS	0.83	9.54	1.36	0.43	9.69
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTS	0.59	0.28	0.2	0.42	0.81
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTS	0.69	0.57	0.4	0.95	1.36
CNTBBCNBBCS	CNT	1.68	31.86	3.15	2.06	32.13
CNTFVTNBBCS	CNT	0.84	8.11	3.93	0.22	9.06
CNTBBCNFVTS	CNT	2.95	37.17	0.27	0.2	37.29
CNTFVTSBBCS	CNT	1.07	6.57	4.21	0.87	7.92
CNTBBCNFVTN	CNT	2.98	39.73	0.83	0.22	39.84
CNTFVTNBBCS	FVTN	1.18	9.48	1.99	0.43	9.77
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTN	0.15	0.66	0.43	0.16	0.82
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTN	0.62	0.21	0.15	0.35	0.76
BBCNFVTNBBCS	FVTN	5.14	1.17	0.83	1.04	5.44
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTN	0.79	0.17	0.12	1.51	1.71
CNTBBCNFVTN	FVTN	3.66	25.29	2.32	1.47	25.7

Table A.4. Total systematic uncertainty estimation (%)

Combination	System	Multi	CNT	PC3	ZVTX	Sum
CNTFVTNBBCS	FVTN	0.2	12.35	1.54	0.39	12.46
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTN	0.3	3.18	0.25	0.33	3.2
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTN	0.2	0.89	0.63	0.24	1.12
BBCNFVTNBBCS	FVTN	0.2	5.61	3.97	5.66	8.91
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTN	0.3	0.58	0.41	0.36	0.8
CNTBBCNFVTN	FVTN	0.2	28.48	5.69	2.1	29.11
CNTFVTNBBCS	FVTN	2.42	21.30	2.09	1.08	21.56
CNTFVTNFVTS	FVTN	5.4	10.50	2.81	0.59	12.16
FVTNFVTSBBCS	FVTN	6.38	4.77	3.37	1.9	8.85
BBCNFVTNBBCS	FVTN	3.74	0.31	0.22	3.92	5.43
BBCNFVTNFVTS	FVTN	4.3	2.84	2.01	0.31	5.55
CNTBBCNFVTN	FVTN	4.11	32.61	2.9	0.61	33
CNTBBCNBBCS	BBCN	4.33	21.61	7.95	3.27	23.66
CNTBBCNFVTS	BBCN	3.91	36.43	2.96	0.84	36.77
BBCNFVTSBBCS	BBCN	4.43	2.02	1.43	2.67	5.73
BBCNFVTNBBCS	BBCN	4.4	0.79	0.56	2.59	5.2
CNTBBCNFVTN	BBCN	3.8	34.46	2.47	0.69	34.77

Bibliography

- [1] K. G. Wilson, Phys. Rev. D **10**, 2445 (1974).
- [2] G. Smoot, S. M. Levin, C. Witebsky, G. D. Amici, and Y. Rephaeli, Astrophys. J. **331** (1988).
- [3] H. D. Politzer, Phys. Rev. Lett. **30**, 1343 (1973).
- [4] D. Griffiths “Introduction to Elementary Particles,” 280–281 (1987).
- [5] M. Gell-Mann, Phys. Rev. **125** (3), 1067–1084 (1962).
- [6] C. S. Fischer and R. Williams, Phys. Rev. Lett. **103**, 122001 (2009).
- [7] D. J. Gross and F. Wilczek, Phys. Rev. Lett. **30**, 1343 (1973).
- [8] Particle Data Group, Phys. Rev. D **86**, 010001 (2012).
- [9] F. Karsch, Lect. Notes Phys. **583** (2002).
- [10] E. Shuryak, Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys. **53** (1), 273–303 (2004).
- [11] R. Snellings, New J. Phys. **13** (2011).

- [12] Z. W. Lin, C. M. Ko, B. A. Li, B. Zhang, and S. Pal, Phys. Rev. C **72**, 064901 (2005).
- [13] A. Adare, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba, and M. Alfred, arXiv:1804.10024 (2018).
- [14] B. Schaefer, Nucl. Phys. A **956**, 545–548 (2016).
- [15] R. Lacey, J. Phys. G **38**, 12 (2011).
- [16] G. Aad, B. Abbott, J. Abdallah, S. A. Khalek, A. A. Abdelalim *et al.*, Phys. Rev. C **86**, 014907 (2012).
- [17] M. Sharma, EPJ WOC **66**, 04027 (2014).
- [18] V. Khachatryan, A. M. Sirunyan, A. Tumasyan, W. Adam, E. Aşlar *et al.*, Phys. Lett. B **765**, 193 (2017).
- [19] S. Chatrchyan, V. Khachatryan, A. M. Sirunyan, A. Tumasyan, W. Adam *et al.*, Phys. Lett. B **718**, 795–814 (2013).
- [20] G. Aad, B. Abbott, J. Abdallah, O. Abidinov, R. Aben *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **116**, 172301 (2016).
- [21] G. Aad, T. Abajyan, B. Abbott, J. Abdallah, S. A. Khalek *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **110**, 182302 (2013).
- [22] Q. Xu, J. Phys. **736**, 1 (2016).

- [23] C. Aidala, Y. Akiba, M. Alfred, K. Aoki, N. Apadula *et al.*, Phys. Rev. C **96**, 064905 (2017).
- [24] C. Aidala, Y. Akiba, M. Alfred, V. Andrieux, K. Aoki *et al.*, Phys. Rev. C **95**, 034910 (2017).
- [25] T. Sakuma, SketchUp STAR, Retrieved from http://people.physics.tamu.edu/sakuma/star/jets/c101218_misc/s0010_sketchup_001/images/rhic.pdf (2014).
- [26] M. Harrison, T. Ludlam, and S. Ozaki, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A **499** (2–3), 235–880 (2003).
- [27] C. Aidala, L. Anaya, E. Anderssen, A. Bambaugh, A. Barron *et al.*, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A **755**, 44–61 (2014).
- [28] K. Adcox, N. N. Ajitanand, J. Alexander, D. Autrey, R. Averbeck *et al.*, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A **499**, 489–507 (2003).
- [29] S. S. Adlera, T. Chujoa, E. J. Desmond, L. Ewella, T. K. Ghosh *et al.*, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A **499** (2–3), 593–602 (2003).
- [30] A. Adare, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba, and H. Al-Bataineh, arXiv:1711.09003
- [31] S. Esumi, PoS CPOD2017 **018** (2018).
- [32] S. Han, S. Esumi, I. Nakagawa, K. Sato, and T. Todoroki, JP18-0277

- [33] A. Bazavov, T. Bhattacharya, C. DeTar, H.-T. Ding, S. Gottlieb *et al.*, Phys. Rev. D **90**, 094503 (2014).
- [34] A. Adare, S. Afanasiev, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **98**, 162301 (2007).
- [35] A. Adare, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba, R. Akimoto *et al.*, Phys. Rev. C **94**, 054910 (2016).
- [36] S. S. Adler, S. Afanasiev, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **94**, 232302 (2005).
- [37] J. Adams, M. M. Aggarwal, Z. Ahammed, J. Amonett, B. D. Anderson *et al.*, Nucl. Phys. **A757**, 102–183 (2005).
- [38] Y. Pandit, J. Phys. Conf. Ser. **458**, 012003 (2013).
- [39] J. Adam, D. Adamova, M. M. Aggarwal, G. A. Rinella, M. Agnello *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **116**, 132302 (2016).
- [40] K. Adcox, S. S. Adler, S. Afanasiev, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand *et al.*, Nucl. Phys. **A757**, 184–283 (2005).
- [41] X. Sun, J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. **535**, 012005 (2014).
- [42] A. Adare, S. Afanasiev, C. Aidala, N. N. Ajitanand, Y. Akiba *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **115**, 142301 (2015).
- [43] B. Alver and G. Roland, Phys. Rev. C **81**, 054905 (2010).

- [44] B. Alver, B. B. Back, M. D. Baker, M. Ballintijn, D. S. Barton *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **98**, 242302 (2007).
- [45] Particle Data Group, Phys. Lett. B. **667**, 1 (2008).
- [46] S. Aoki, K.-I. Ishikawa, N. Ishizuka, T. Izubuchi, D. Kadoh *et al.*, Phys. Rev. D **79**, 034503 (2009).